

ONLINE EDUCATION AND ITS OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract. The article discusses the content, functions, benefits, and drawbacks of virtual learning management systems in distance education, as well as their practical opportunities in higher education institutions.

Key words: Distance Education, Distance Teaching, Distance Education in Higher Education, Learning Management System (LMS), Distance Learning System, Online Education, Online Courses, E-learning, Innovative Education, Distance Education, Technologies.

Introduction. Distance Education (DE) is a type of learning in which the teacher and student are separated by distance or time, utilizing information technologies. There are several models of this type of education, which differ depending on the circumstances that led to the organization of distance education: Geographic reasons (the country's size, existence of geographically remote regions from the centers). The level of computerization and informatization in the country. The development of transportation and communication. Availability of specialists for distance education. The degree of use of information and communication technologies in the education sector. National customs in the field of education.

Distance education, also known as **e-learning** or **online education**, is characterized by physical separation between teachers and students during the teaching process, and includes the use of various technologies to facilitate communication between students and teachers, and between students themselves. Distance education traditionally targets non-traditional students, such as working professionals, military personnel, non-residents, or people in remote areas who cannot attend in-person lectures. However, as distance education has become a key component of global education, trends indicate its continuous growth.

In recent years, new reforms have been launched in Uzbekistan's national education system. Education management has been subject to severe criticism from government leaders. Normative-legal documents aimed at improving mechanisms for managing the national education system were developed with a

systematic, innovative approach. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PD-3775 of June 5, 2018, "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in large-scale reforms in the country," became the legal basis for the fundamental changes in Uzbekistan's education sector. Based on this law, important reforms included the creation of new higher education institutions in the regions, the opening of modern educational and specialization areas, as well as the expansion of correspondence and evening education departments, and increasing the admission quotas for universities. Now, introducing modern teaching methods, including blended learning, has become increasingly important. Strengthening effective innovations through regulation in education is also a critical task. In October 2019, the "Concept for the Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted. An important innovation was the gradual transition to a credit-module system in higher education institutions. During the pandemic, the events planned under the 2030 Development Concept were accelerated unexpectedly and, in many ways, obligatorily. To adequately address the challenges, it was necessary to reorganize the entire education system, including not only higher education but also secondary schools and even preschool education. In a short period, Uzbekistan's entire education system was restructured and launched based on digital and distance learning principles.

The COVID-19 pandemic and the associated quarantine not only disrupted the usual way of life and people's labor activities but also opened new opportunities for organizing civil society behavior. This was fully relevant to the education system, where restrictions on the mobility of participants required the urgent establishment of an education process. In these circumstances, distance education played a key role in maintaining the continuity of education.

In order to ensure the continuity of the educational process in the country's higher education institutions and provide methodological support for students' learning activities remotely, distance education platforms were launched on April 1, 2020. These platforms primarily provided students with the opportunity to organize learning in a completely new format by creating virtual classrooms where students and teachers could interact.

The **Distance Learning System** is software that supports the organization of distance learning, the management of educational processes, the circulation of electronic documents, the creation of electronic learning materials, and the

evaluation of progress. It also enables the use of Internet technologies for teaching when the teacher and student are geographically separated.

Modern education offers various forms: full-time, correspondence, evening, and distance education. Distance education, in line with current societal development, is the most relevant type of education. Unlike traditional forms, distance education is implemented using telecommunications technologies and the latest innovations in the field of the Internet. Distance education systems can train schoolchildren, university students, and even workers in preparation for employment. Currently, the distance education system is implemented through ready-to-install software products, such as MS Office, where courses are created after studying the user manual or completing a brief training course.

Any distance learning system is a systematic information package used to plan and conduct all distance education activities, often in conjunction with full-time, evening, and correspondence programs. In foreign countries, such systems are usually called **Learning Management Systems (LMS)**, reflecting their extended functionality and their significant role in the operation of educational institutions.

Learning Management System (LMS) capabilities: Establishing an additional system to support the educational process. Organizing educational activities and testing the qualifications of employees in corporate centers and commercial organizations. Conducting distance education when students are physically removed from the education space, such as when they subscribe to specific topics or courses, receive methodological guidance, and complete specific assignments or tests. Managing the educational process in educational centers, courses, and universities, improving quality, increasing the number of students taught simultaneously.

Distance Learning System tasks: Automating and centralizing the management of the educational process. Uploading educational materials to provide students access. Maintaining the relevance of Distance Learning Technology (DLT) standards. Ensuring the reuse of educational materials and personalizing the content. Expanding cooperation among participants in the educational process. Increasing learning efficiency and reducing educational costs. Simplifying monitoring the effectiveness of educational programs.

Each company, organization, or institution has its own needs when it comes to solving distance education issues. To understand which system is required, it is necessary to evaluate all LMS systems available on the market. Only after this can the integration processes within the organization begin. For those who have

just started creating online courses, understanding the development of distance learning systems is crucial. After all, electronic education is an integral part of LMS.

There are eight key reasons why this system is important: **All data in one place:** Educational materials can be centralized, eliminating the need for disks or other physical media. This makes learning more accessible and reduces the risk of data loss. **Free access to necessary content:** E-learning courses can be accessed not only on personal computers but also through smartphones and other innovative gadgets. All data is stored on a single server. **Analysis of the learning process:** Unlike traditional classes, LMS allows for tracking progress and ensures completion. If a student does not grasp the material, other resources can be recommended to improve learning outcomes. **Minimal costs:** Traditional classes involve various expenses such as renting facilities, while distance learning reduces costs associated with these issues. **Higher efficiency:** LMS removes unnecessary components from lessons, allowing students to focus on essential content. **Customization to meet organizational standards:** Online courses are adapted to meet the standards approved by the administration, allowing flexibility and rapid updates to new requirements. **Material updates:** Scientific work is constantly updated, allowing the curriculum to be modified in real-time to reflect the latest research.

LMS Advantages: **Accessibility:** Students can study from almost any location. **Cost reduction:** Saves on materials and infrastructure costs. **Flexibility:** The educational process can be adapted to the needs and capabilities of teachers and students. **Modern development:** Electronic courses allow the users (teachers and students) to continuously improve their skills in line with the latest technologies. **Objective assessment:** Electronic education provides clear criteria to evaluate the knowledge gained by the student. **Platform Features:** **Moodle Free** platform – Offers wide customization options with many plugins to extend functionality. Requires web development skills for administration. **iSpring** – A platform for the corporate sector that enables the creation of various types of training materials, webinars, and detailed statistics. **WebTutor** – A modular HRM platform that facilitates comprehensive personnel management processes. **Teachbase** – A cloud-based educational platform that supports course creation and sales. **GetCourse** – A popular platform for info-businessmen with webinar capabilities and various payment integrations. **Memberlux** – A plugin for WordPress that allows creating a learning portal for a one-time fee, suitable for entrepreneurs.

Conclusion. A well-developed technological infrastructure is essential for the implementation of LMS. Teachers need to be ready to adapt their curricula to e-learning. With the help of distance learning technologies, it is possible not only to transfer a range of regular pedagogical activities to computers but also to organize truly high-quality, individualized, and differentiated education.

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